

A quick look in the recognition and sensing of fluoride anion[†]

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Abstract : The fluorine element is the most electronegative and its anion has strong nucleophilic character and behaves as relatively strong Bronsted base. The properties make fluoride ion fond of hydrogen bond interactions. In this manuscript fluoride binding properties in structurally varied molecular structures are exploited.

Keywords : Fluoride ions, their binding, recognition and sensing.

Introduction

Molecular recognition represents the central event at the basis of many fundamental chemical and biological phenomena, such as catalysis, transport and sensing, and it also constitutes a topic of foremost importance in supramolecular chemistry. During last few decades, deeper understanding of the various roles that anions play in biology, industrial processes and in the environment, recognition of anionic species has indeed become a mature area of research¹. It has been pointed out that the variety of shapes, charges and dimensions of anions represented in the past had a reason for the late development of the field when compared to that of cation recognition, which matured earlier and faster². On the other hand, the intrinsic properties of a given anion can be exploited, to achieve that high degree of selectivity and affinity which would make a novel receptor practical for real-world applications. Therefore, it was found useful to review the literature from the anion's perspective by focusing on a single anion and then evaluating the efforts towards achieving its binding with respect to its characteristic features.

As a chemical entity, the fluoride anion is a quite peculiar species. Being the smallest halide, it has a highest charge density, however, its dimension cannot be considered small since its ionic radius is approximately the same as that of K⁺³. The F element is the most electronegative, and F⁻ has a strong nucleophilic character.

Moreover, it can behave as a relatively strong Bronsted base. All this makes fluoride particularly fond of hydrogen bonding (HB) partners. This article embodies a concise information on the recent developments of receptors for the sensing of fluoride ions using H-bonding interactions.

Hydrogen bonding receptors

Hydrogen bonding interactions are always elicited first whenever anion binding is sought and, by no surprise, the vast majority of anion receptors are precisely designed to rely on those. Most strikingly, hydrogen bondings are indeed the intermolecular forces selected by Nature to bind anions to proteins. A well known and often cited example is given by the binding of chloride attained by the chloride channels studied by Dutzler *et al.*⁴. The chloride anion is clearly establishing hydrogen bond interactions with OH groups in tyrosine and serine residues, but also with amidic NHs on the protein backbone. As to fluoride complexes, to the best of our knowledge, there are only few recent examples of isolated hydrogen bonding driven fluoride-protein complexes⁵. However, more structures are expected to be published in the near future since fluoride is indeed becoming a useful reagent for trapping the oxyanion hole in protein active sites⁶. Strong hydrogen bonding interactions can lead to the deprotonation of the hydrogen bonding donor moiety, thus making the complexation with the anion infeasible. Moreover, in systems having relatively acidic NH or OH

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

effect of fluoride binding on the signals belonging to the fluorinated phenyl rings in **1**. Fluoride itself can be monitored by ^{19}F NMR spectrum. Upon complexation with **1**, fluoride anion experiences a downfield shift, as commonly observed also in other studies. Single crystal X-ray study showed that the fluoride anion is tightly bound inside the cavity formed by the six amidic NHs in a nearly perfect octahedral binding mode with N-H...F $^-$ hydrogen bonding distances varying between 1.90 and 2.15 Å (N-H...F angles in the range of 149.2–164.81). Different, but equally electron-poor substituted phenyl rings are employed in the tris-(thio)urea derivatives **2a** and **2b** (Scheme 1)¹⁵. Binding in solution is detected by ^1H and ^{19}F NMR. As far as the binding of **2a** with halides is concerned, no particularly remarkable differences are found with respect to the behaviour of **1**. Compound **2b**, having the aromatic rings substituted at the *para* position with CN groups, binds to fluoride in DMSO- d_6 ($\log K = 4.51$) almost 25 times more efficiently than to Cl $^-$ and more than 600 times better than to Br $^-$ and I $^-$, thus being the best receptor for fluoride among the three species (**1**, **2a** and **2b**)^{15b}. A very similar design is also employed in compound **3** (Scheme 1), which has electrochemically active ferrocenyl groups appended at the end of the three urea arms¹⁶. The study conducted on the series of compounds **4a-c** and **4d** (Scheme 1)¹⁷, similar to the previously described ones, but having a single amidic NH per sidearm. Study on how the position and the number of NO $_2$ groups on the phenyl rings may induce differences on the binding attitude of a series of compounds revealed interesting aspects of the association event. Among the series of monosubstituted NO $_2$ derivatives^{17a} it is claimed that **4a** has the highest affinities for F $^-$ in DMSO in the lot. Compound **4d**, studied by a different group, possesses doubly NO $_2^-$ substituted sidearms^{17b}. Interestingly, a 10^{-5} M solution of **4d** changes colour dramatically by

the addition of a large excess of F $^-$ (1000 times) in DMSO, and this event, visible by the naked-eye, is not produced by any other halide or other common oxyanions. Such a phenomenon is related to the appearance of an intense band on the absorption spectrum centred at around 537 nm in DMSO and strongly solvent dependent. ^1H and ^{19}F NMR investigations were undertaken. Fitting the chemical shift's variation of the NH protons observed in a 20 mM solution of **4d** upon increasing fluoride concentration, an apparent binding constant of 10^7 M $^{-1}$ was calculated. In our lab, we have synthesized and characterized bispentafluorophenylcarbohydrazone **6** and the corresponding thiocarbohydrazone **7**¹⁸. Both compounds show efficient intermolecular interactions with fluoride anions. However, compound **7** binds F $^-$ selectively with a large binding constant (3.09×10^5). This interaction is visible to naked eye. Theoretical calculations (DFT and TD DFT) also support these experimental results.

Binding of fluoride as ion-pair

Receptors having a heteroditopic nature and being able to bind simultaneously a cation and an anion, i.e. an ion pair, are extremely interesting species. The most common strategy employed in order to build up an ion-pair receptor is simply based on the linking up of two classical anions and cations binding sites into a unified structure. Thus, it is not surprising that most of the ion-pair receptors are constituted by calix[n]arene or crown-ether-like moieties, acting as cation recognition sites, conjugated with tetra-pyrroles, porphyrins or amidic/ureidic sidearms, providing the binding to the anion. The calix[4]arene strapped calix[4]pyrrole **8** (Scheme 3)¹⁹ is built by connecting two well-known ion binding sites. In CDCl $_3$, fluoride (added as TBA salt) strongly binds to the calixpyrrole moiety. However, very different behaviour is observed when the solvent was made more competitive

Scheme 2

by adding 10% v/v of methanol. Under such conditions, no changes of chemical shift of any receptor's signals were observed, consistently with a much lower affinity for fluoride.

The addition of CsF, under the same conditions, caused significant changes in the proton signals of both the calix[4]arene and the calix[4]pyrrole moieties, the former changes fully consistent with an 1,3 alternate conformation of the cation binding site. After testing alkali metal salts, it was also proven that the binding of fluoride occurs only with the concurring binding of Cs⁺ ion. Also, while complexes of cesium halides can be formed, in a mixture of CsF, CsCl, CsBr and CsNO₃, the only complex produced corresponds to the CsF adduct.

Scheme 3. Structure of calix[4]arene strapped calix[4]pyrrole **8**.

Conclusion

Considering the multifaceted nature and the number of fields in which fluoride has established its relevance, there is steady increase in the number of publications which report on studies related to fluoride binding, recognition and sensing.

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